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Deciphering Sustainability Messages in Audio-Visual Advertisements toward achieving the SDGs

Abstract

India is one of those countries that, along with other countries across the world has taken a pledge to protect the environment, as well as promote overall development through sustainable practices. The Government of India like other nations is trying to promote initiatives that help it in achieving these goals. Amid such developments, even corporate organizations are attempting to include such practices in their functioning through innovative advertisements. Not just creation, but marketing and promotion of products and services by both international and Indian brands reflect the goals through their commercials that aim to be fulfilled by 2030. While creating advertisements with direct and indirect approaches alone are not sufficient to spread awareness, the reception of the messages and understanding of the concept is actually important in implementing the SDGs into practice. Such endeavors highly resonate and click with today's fairly educated and literate (also 'woke') audience who makes conscious and informed purchasing decisions. The study considered selected advertisements to map the SDGs embedded into the messages. In this regard, Focus Group Discussions were conducted to 1. evaluate the perception of the participants who were exposed to the ads and a2. to elicit suggestions that could be utilized to disseminate the goals to the masses with a higher impact and widen the sphere of application of the global effort to achieve sustainability.

Keywords: sustainability, audio-visual advertisements, perception, awareness, SDGs

Introduction

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Sustainable Development Goals

The World Charter for Nature of 1982 adopted by the United Nations proclaims principles of conservation with guided human conduct leading to the protection of 'nature' against degradation from human hostility, consequently denoting the idea of 'sustainability'. The idea of sustainable development as an idea envelopes 'efficient use of resources' and 'continued economic growth' evolved in the 1992 Earth Summit. 'Our Common Future', the report published by the Brundtland Commission in 1987 elucidates sustainability as the development achieved through long-term strategies and social integration while conserving the potential resources for the future. The definition of sustainability was further extended to encompass social development in the World Summit on Social Development in Copenhagen in 1995 and is pertinent in the document published by the UN as the "The Future We Want" adopted at the Rio conference in 2012.¹ The recommendation of the report 'The Future We Want' resulted in the formation of the 'Open Working Group' (OWG) for the execution of the development goals for sustainability. This group continues to meet new targets with the cooperation of the United Nations and actively lends support to the fulfillment of the (Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)).² 'Sustainability' acknowledges the basic requirements of human life but seeks to establish an equal distribution of limited resources and thus lights up the path of sustainable development for the advancement of society as a whole. This idea is reflected in the report "Our Common Journey: A Transition toward Sustainability" published by the U.S. National Academy of Science also committed to the sustenance of those preliminary areas which are the 'life support system' and 'nature'. The report also indicates that addressing environmental problems such as the preservation of biodiversity and climate is equally important as marking progress in other areas of human development such as food and energy.³

A measure undertaken by the United Nations led to the establishment of MDGs to ensure development through sustainability, like 'promotion of global partnership, universal education and gender equality', 'combating HIV/AIDS and betterment of maternal healthcare facilities' and 'abolishment of poverty and hunger'.⁴ These MDGs have been adhered to and continued efforts have brought in large-scale advancements like the Republic of China reduced its poverty rate to half in 10 years. The measurement of the impact of sustainability is important and simultaneously the resultant advancement has to be portrayed for the application of the concept of sustainability in the decided sectors. The values to ensure sustainable development in belief

and behavior are crucial along with the enactment of the principles leading to the accomplishment of the goals enshrined in the charter for sustainability as was understood from the various efforts implemented before.⁵ SDGs are objectives set by member states of the United Nations in 2015 to bring peace and prosperity universally as there is substantial information to prove the alignment of development efforts with a continuous approach. The resolution looks forward to focusing on the five core spheres like People, Planet, Prosperity, Peace, and Partnerships which will primarily be essential to cause progress globally. Thus, in a nutshell, the SDGs are framed to direct overall (social, economic, and environmental) growth.⁶ The implementation of the SDGs would be successful upon following the ‘triple bottom line approach’ where the developed countries pledged that they would provide financial and technological contributions to the developing and underdeveloped nations. The requisite administration of the entire blueprint for SDGs is the fourth tier which interconnects the other three bottom lines of sustainable development.⁷

The 17 SDGs adopted by the member countries of the United Nations ‘no poverty’, ‘zero hunger’, ‘good health and wellbeing’, ‘quality education’, ‘gender equality’, ‘clean water and sanitation’, ‘affordable and clean energy’, ‘decent work and economic growth’, ‘industry, innovation, and infrastructure’, ‘reduce inequalities’, ‘sustainable cities and communities’, ‘responsible consumption and production’, ‘climate action’, ‘life below water’, ‘life on land’, ‘peace, justice, and strong institution’ and ‘partnerships for the global’ are all linked with each other. The wedding cake (image 1) reflecting sustainability that can be only achieved by first protecting the first tier i.e., the environment, followed by the growth of the society and economics through continued joint efforts of all the nations.⁸

Figure 1- Management Development Goals, Sustainable Development Goals, and SDGs Wedding cake, source: The United Nations (www.un.org) and Stockholm Resilience Center (2016)

India's achievement in sustainability

After gaining independence from British rule, India placed trust in the 'pragmatic approach' of strengthening the economy and the Gandhian concept of sustainability was largely overlooked. Whereas, the socialist ideology further strengthened in 1954 when the economy focused on public enterprises, and 1976 saw the addition of the word 'socialist' to the preamble. At the time, emphasis was given to results rather than the process to create development in a haste ignoring the preservation of climate and biodiversity.⁹ In 2014, the Planning Commission assigned with the hefty task of uplifting the nation was replaced by Institution for Transforming India (Niti-Ayog). The Indian Government with the Niti-Ayog works in consonance with the United Nation's SDGs and has since launched a number of schemes like Swachh-Bharat, Mission Indhradhanush, PM-JAY and publishes SDG index to keep track of their growth.¹⁰

Fig 2: Sustainable Development Goals score for India and the performance of the nation across various goals, 2022. Source: sdgindex.org

India stands at a global rank of 12 with the score of 60.32 (a regional average of 65.90). This being the cumulative score, India has made significant growth in areas like ‘climate action’, ‘responsible consumption and production’ however ‘gender equality’, ‘reduced inequality’ need more attention to be able to be effective.¹¹

The SDG Index is a tool to map the progress of the Indian States and Union Territories on the global goals with 115 indicators in order to observe the status of the execution of the task and endorse an environment of competition.

Fig3: SDG Index Composite score of India, Source: SDG India Index and Dashboard 2020–21: Partnerships in the Decade of Action

India scores 66 in the SDG India Index and dashboard 2020–21: Partnerships in the Decade of Action, report published by NITI Aayog and has performed extraordinarily in Goal 6 (Clean Water and Sanitation) and Goal 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy) and Uttarakhand, Gujarat, Maharashtra, Mizoram, Punjab, Haryana, Tripura, Delhi, Lakshadweep, Andaman and Nicobar Islands, Jammu and Kashmir and Ladakh score the highest.¹² The inception of many programs by the government like the mid-day meal, ‘*Samagra Shiksha Abhiyan*’ for education, ‘*Pradhan Mantri Ujjwala Yojana*’, ‘*Beti-Bachao Beti-Padhao*’, ‘*Sukanya Samridhi*’ for gender equality, ‘*Pradhan Mantri Sahaj Bijli Har Ghar Yojana- Saubhagya*’, for affordable and clean energy and many more have contributed to the phenomenal growth which India has shown.

Scope of the study

The positioning of a brand as carbon-neutral or eco-friendly has its own benefits as consumers often prefer these values to be attached to the brands when opting for a product. The role of the advertisement has always played a significant part in disseminating ideas and information across the mass, especially the audio-visual advertisement has the ability to reach out to less-informed people, unlike other media vehicles. This study aims to decipher the message shared through audio-visual commercials to understand their connections with SDGs, at the same time the perception possessed by the audience.

Methodology

In order to interpret the sustainable goals and vision of the major companies around the world, selective advertisement campaigns were studied and analyzed to look out for the relevance of

the advertisements connected with the SDGs. Narrative reviews were conducted to screen each one of the twelve advertisements. The study further extends its analysis through Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) with students and academicians segregated into two controlled groups.

1. Controlled group one: Students between the age of 18 to 22.
2. Controlled group two: Academicians between the age of 23 to 40.

Objectives

- To identify the areas of development required to achieve sustainability for India from a global standpoint for achieving the SDGs.
- To assess the mapping of SDGs in both direct and indirect approaches of audio-visual advertisements.
- To understand the perception of the audience on the Indian and international audio-visual advertisements.

Result and Analysis

The performance of SDGs is strictly monitored by the ‘Division of Sustainable Development Goals’ (DSDG) under the ‘Department of Economic and Social Affairs, UN’ (UNDESA) since its inception across all of its events (598), publications (456), and actions (20,436) combined

Fig 4: Status of SDGs among the member state, 2022, Source: Sustainable Development Report 2022, United Nations

The 2022 report on the performance of SDGs across the member states shows (image 4) the fluctuation of seventeen goals across the nations. ‘Climate change’ was observed to be achieved by 64 nations, considered as the highest among the rest while unfortunately. ‘No poverty’, ‘industry, innovation and infrastructure’, and ‘life below water’ are the least developed areas that require more actions to be taken for a majority of the nations.

Fig 5: India's score for 17 SDGs along with SDG index score for last seven years,

Source: Sustainable Development Report 2022, United Nations

India, being one of the founding nations of UN since the inception, is also coming under the preview of the SDGs and is currently ranked 121 among the 196 nations. Since 2015, the nation evolved and implemented countless initiatives to improve its sustainability (image 5), however, some areas like 'industry, innovation, and infrastructure' and 'gender equality' requires a lot more penetration and attention to achieve even a marginal score compared to the other goals. On the other hand, 'equality and education', 'climate action', and 'responsible consumption' and 'production' are seen to be achieving sustainability faster and better than in other areas.

Advertisements are one of the most potent ways to send a message across to a large number of people. It can be shared and reshared over social media and digital media platforms to multiply the impact and thus end up reaching even a wide range of audience. Audio-visual ads have the ability to convey the message with more intensity as the dual benefits it provides to the audience manages to capture and retain their interest for a longer period of time.

International Advertisements depicting Sustainable Development Goals: Direct Approach

Seven Billion Dreams- UN Environment Programme, is a commercial by the United Nations that runs through a series of stunning visuals that constantly compare nature with the brutality that we are posing on it. The two-minute commercial is actually soothingly subdivided into

three distinctive but blended parts, the beauty of lustful nature, the harms that we are continuously inflicting on it, and the measures towards sustainability that we should adopt to protect and sustain this planet and its environment. The audio-visual commercial boost and encourage the usage of ‘using LED to save energy while reducing energy wastage’, ‘using sustainable energy resources (wind and solar energy)’, ‘increasing green harvesting’, ‘switching to low heat consumption’, ‘reducing water wastage’, ‘increasing waste recycling’, ‘improving education’ and ‘developing sustainable technology’.

The Power of Sustainability- Henkel, is an advertisement that directly aims at evoking our responsibilities towards the earth to protect and sustain the natural resources. The ad urges us to take sustainable steps through ‘creating smarter packaging’, ‘choosing ingredients with higher environmental and social standards’, ‘enabling circular economy’, ‘switching to low carbon transportation’, ‘building state of the art factories that uses less and greener power’, ‘exploring and manufacturing sustainable technology’ and ‘using products reduce the water and energy wastage’.

Climate action starts at home- IKEA, is a commercial that complements the idea of living a balanced life that resonates the responsible consumption across all levels and imbibe the spirit of sustainability through our lifestyle. The commercial explores and recommends a number of ways through which sustainability can be approached and incorporated into our activities like ‘powering home with solar power’, ‘using low-flow shower and tap’, ‘air drying laundries’, ‘reusing leftover food’, ‘using environment-friendly accessories (bag)’, ‘using cycle instead of car’, ‘availing public transportation rather than personal transportation’, ‘recycling trash’, ‘consuming fresh and organic products’, ‘reusing products’, ‘growing organic food for individual usage’, ‘using pressure cooker for energy saving’, ‘consuming more greens’, ‘using green power for cars’, ‘using natural ways to cool down temperature rather than using air conditioner’ and ‘using LEDs for lesser power consumption’.

International Advertisements depicting Sustainable Development Goals: Indirect Approach

Every product carbon neutral by 2030- Apple, is a straightaway approach towards being carbon neutral, leading a sustainable way of production and consumption of resources. The steps that are being mentioned in the advertisement are directly or indirectly leading to a sustainable production and consumption of resources not only in producing the apple products but to extend the good practices among its ecosystem through ‘making every Apple product carbon

neutral by 2030', 'making all their products a hundred percent recycled or renewable', 'inventing ways to extract materials from the old Apple products for reuse', 'harvesting trees to supplement the requirement of paper for packaging their products', 'strengthening and encouraging the use of renewable energy for production even among their partners', 'going zero waste' and 'aiming to make the electricity consumption of Apple products a hundred percent renewable by 2030'.

Parallel Lives- HP, is a short but interesting commercial that narrates the story of a fish and a plastic bag from the point of their origin in the ocean and factory, till they meet at in the ocean. The concept is based on the pollution of water bodies caused by the plastics that can be collected and reused in making usable products. The commercial is aiming for one single SGD through its approach 'so far, over fifty HP products contains ocean-bound plastic'.

Let's create a world that runs entirely on green energy- Orsted, is an advertisement based on the transition of non-renewable to renewable energy. The audio-visual is also urging people to take care of the one large home (earth) that we share with millions of other humans, animals, plants and organisms. Although the ad seems to focus on a specific area of sustainability, it actually includes few other areas of SDGs like 'no more production of oil and gas', 'prohibiting all the usage of coals', 'Focusing entirely on green energy', 'building largest offshore wind operation', 'enriching civilizations from powers generated from the see', 'helping the world to run entirely on green energy' and 'encouraging people to take positive actions towards sustainability'.

Indian Advertisements depicting Sustainable Development Goals: Direct Approach

Weaving Rural India's Sustainable Development agenda into our own carbon neutral commitment- Infosys, is an advertisement that is directly targeting several SDGS through the different audio-visuals. s. Although the ad is primarily focusing on the climatic change and the preventive actions to be taken to minimize the impact, the commercial also reached out to cover multiple SDGs throughout its over three-minutes presentation like 'carbon neutral program', 'reducing firewood usage', 'better utilization of cattle dung', 'carbon offset program', 'setting up bio-gas units', 'generating clean cooking gas from cattle dung', 'producing manure to be used as organic fertilizer', 'distributing improved cooking stoves', 'helping women in pursuing other occupations', 'addressing issues of health', 'improving

education’, ‘reducing pollutions’, ‘saving forest’, ‘empowering women’, ‘reducing pollutants like CO₂’, and ‘aiming to become carbon neutral by March 2020’.

Digital India for Sustainable Development Goals- Digital India, is a commercial from the Government of India to relate sustainability with the digital India initiative. The ad reaches out to the vast and diverse population of India through multiple initiatives that emanates sustainability like ‘enhancement of digital infrastructure services’, ‘digital empowerment’, ‘end poverty’, ‘end hunger’, ‘improve health’, ‘provide quality education’, ‘create a cleaner and safer environment’, encouraging collaboration with governments and between industries’, ‘supporting through common service centre’s’, ‘providing essential services to citizens’, ‘improving agriculture’, ‘improving public distribution’, ‘aiming food security’, ‘lead and share knowledge’, and ‘sharing experience and capabilities with the world’.

India's progress towards achieving the Sustainable Development Goals- United Nations in India, is yet another advertisement from the United Nation India, relating the growth and development of the nation with sustainability. The agenda under “sabka saath sabka vikas” leads to the fulfilment of the goals through various initiatives like ‘booming economy’, ‘reducing the number of people who are living in poverty’, ‘increasing the production capacity of sustainable energy’, ‘empowering women’, ‘supporting social security system’, ‘offering job guarantees’, ‘better cleanliness’, ‘construction of toilets’, ‘supporting healthcare’, ‘ensuring food security’, ‘improving food distribution’, ‘saving girl child’, ‘self-government for women at village level’, ‘Space technology development’, ‘improved foreign policy development’ and ‘developing international alliance’.

Indian Advertisements depicting Sustainable Development Goals: Indirect Approach

Let's raise a generation of equals- Flipkart, is targeting the fifth SDG ‘gender equality’ through this advertisement and brings in a series of audio-visuials that lays out the fact of stereotyping mentality of the society when it comes to gender. The commercial displays a series of quotes like ‘boys don’t play with dolls’, ‘girls don’t like cars’, ‘you’re crying like a girl’, and ‘OMG! It’s a girl’ are tagged on the kids based on their gender. Eventually, the ad concentrates on approaches that are not restricted to a specific gender like ‘a boy can cry the same way as a girl’, ‘a girl can like cars the same way a boy’, ‘pink can be the favorite color of both’, ‘both a boy and girl can have a passion for sports’, ‘a boy can learn the household work like a girl is

taught', 'both a boy and a girl can have the same aspiration', 'both of them can dream to become a ballet dancer' or 'to become a superhero'.

ITC Water story- ITC Corp Com, featured their effort which was a part of their corporate communication and CSR initiative towards sustainability. The 'ITC water project' covered 16 states and 43 districts to help them with water-related issues. The commercial highlights various areas that are coming under sustainable development like 'water reservation', 'distribution', and 'usage' for multiple villages to help them in 'irrigation', 'domestic water usage', 'sustaining ecological balances', and 'improving the economy'.

Munni- P&G Shiksha, was one of the campaigns from Procter & Gamble Corporation (P&G) that emphasized the importance of essential and quality education for children. This is an interesting approach to narrating the story of Munni, who was upset about not being able to go to school, however she gets the chance to attend school through the P&G Shiksha initiative that urged its customers to buy their products so that they can continue their contribution to building school and infrastructure for supporting education.

Table 1: International audio-visual campaigns (direct and indirect approach) connecting SDGs

International Advertisements aiming SDGs							
Audio-Visual Campaigns catering to sustainable development – <i>Direct approach</i>			Audio-Visual Campaigns catering to sustainable development – <i>Indirect approach</i>				
Ad Campaign	Ad Content indicating SDGs	Targeted SDGs	Year	Ad Campaign	Ad Content indicating SDGs	Targeted SDGs	Year
<i>Seven Billion Dreams- UN Environment Programme</i>	Using LED to save energy while reducing energy wastage.	Affordable and clean energy	2015	<i>Every product carbon neutral by 2030</i>	Making every Apple product carbon neutral by 2030	Industry, innovation, and infrastructure	2021
	Using sustainable energy resources (wind and solar energy)	Affordable and clean energy			Making all their products a hundred percent recycled or renewable	Climate action	
	Increasing green harvesting	Sustainable cities and communities			Inventing ways to extract materials from the old Apple products for reuse	Responsible consumption and production	
	Switching to low heat consumption	Responsible consumption and production			Harvesting trees to supplement the requirement of paper for packaging their products	Life on land	
	Reducing water wastage	Sustainable cities and communities			Strengthening and encouraging the use of renewable energy for production even among their partners	Partnerships for the global	

<i>The Power of Sustainability- Henkel</i>	Increasing waste recycling	Sustainable cities and communities	2018	<i>Sustainability Parallel Live</i>	Going zero waste	Responsible consumption and production	2021
	Improving education	Quality Education					
	Developing sustainable technology	Industry, innovation, and infrastructure					
	Creating smarter packaging	Industry, innovation, and infrastructure					
	Choosing ingredients with higher environmental and social standards	Responsible consumption and production					
	Enabling circular economy	Responsible consumption and production					
	Switching to low carbon transportation	Sustainable cities and communities					
	Building state of the art factories that uses less and greener power	Sustainable cities and communities					
	Exploring and manufacturing sustainable technology	Industry, innovation, and infrastructure					
	Using products reduce the water and energy wastage	Industry, innovation, and infrastructure					
<i>Climate action starts at home</i>	Powering home with solar power	Sustainable cities and communities	2019	<i>Let's create a world that runs entirely</i>	No more production of oil and gas	Responsible consumption and production	2017

	<p>Using low-flow shower and tap</p> <p>Air drying laundries</p> <p>Reusing leftover food</p> <p>Using environment-friendly accessories (bag)</p> <p>Using cycle instead of car</p> <p>Availing public transportation rather than personal transportation</p> <p>Recycling trash</p> <p>Consuming fresh and organic products</p> <p>Reusing products</p>	<p>Industry, innovation, and infrastructure</p> <p>Responsible consumption and production</p> <p>Responsible consumption and production</p> <p>Industry, innovation, and infrastructure</p> <p>Responsible consumption and production</p> <p>Responsible consumption and production</p> <p>Responsible consumption and production</p> <p>Responsible consumption and production</p> <p>Good health and wellbeing</p> <p>Responsible consumption and production</p>	<p><i>on green energy</i></p>	<p>Prohibiting all the usage of coals</p> <p>Focusing entirely on green energy</p> <p>Building largest offshore wind operation</p> <p>Enriching civilizations from powers generated from the sea</p> <p>Helping the world to run entirely on green energy</p> <p>Encouraging people to take positive actions towards sustainability</p>	<p>Responsible consumption and production</p> <p>Affordable and clean energy</p> <p>Affordable and clean energy</p> <p>Sustainable cities and communities</p> <p>Affordable and clean energy</p> <p>Partnerships for the global</p>
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Table 2: Indian audio-visual campaigns (direct and indirect approach) connecting SDGs
Indian Advertisements aiming SDGs

Audio-Visual Campaigns catering to sustainable development – Direct approach			Audio-Visual Campaigns catering to sustainable development – Indirect approach					
Ad Campaign	Ad Content indicating SDGs	Targeted SDGs	Ad Campaign	Ad Content indicating SDGs	Targeted SDGs			
<i>Weaving Rural India's Sustainable Development agenda into our own carbon neutral commitment</i>	Carbon neutral program	Climate action	<i>Let's raise a generation of equals!</i>	A boy can cry the same as a girl	Gender equality			
	Reducing firewood usage	Life on land		A girl can like cars the same way a boy				
	Better utilization of cattle dung	Sustainable cities and communities		Pink can be the favorite color of both				
	Carbon offset program	Climate action		Both a boy and girl can have a passion for sports				
	Setting up bio-gas units	Industry, innovation, and infrastructure		A boy can learn the household works like a girl is taught				
	Generating clean cooking gas from cattle dung	Affordable and clean energy		Both a boy and a girl can have the same aspiration				
	Producing manure to be used as organic fertilizer	Industry, innovation, and infrastructure		Both of them can dream to become a ballet dancer				
	Distributing improved cooking stoves	Industry, innovation, and infrastructure		Both of them can dream to become a superhero				
	Helping women in pursuing other occupations	Decent work and economic growth						
	Addressing issues of health	Good health and wellbeing						
								2018

<i>Digital India for Sustainable Development Goals</i>	Improving education	Quality Education	<i>ITC Water story</i>	2017	2019		
	Reducing pollutions	Climate action				Solve irrigation-related problems	Decent work and economic growth
	Saving forest	Life on land				Improving water reservation	Industry, innovation, and infrastructure
	Empowering women	Gender equality				Improving water distribution	Industry, innovation, and infrastructure
	Reducing pollutants like CO ₂	Climate action				Improving water usage	Clean water and sanitation
	Aiming to become carbon neutral by March 2020	Climate action Responsible consumption and production				Water usage in irrigation	Industry, innovation, and infrastructure
	Enhancement of digital infrastructure services	Industry, innovation, and infrastructure				Domestic water usage	Clean water and sanitation
	Digital empowerment	Decent work and economic growth				Sustaining ecological balances	Climate action Life on land
	End poverty	No poverty					
	End hunger	Zero hunger					
Improve health	Good health and wellbeing						
Provide quality education	Quality Education						
Create a cleaner and safer environment	Clean water and sanitation Peace, justice, and strong institution						

<i>India's progress towards achieving the Sustainable Development Goals</i>	Encouraging collaboration with governments and between industries	Partnerships for the global	<i>P&G Shiksha Mummy</i>	Improving economy	Decent work and economic growth	2021
	Supporting through common service centers	Partnerships for the global				
	Providing essential services to citizens	Sustainable cities and communities				
	Improving agriculture	Industry, innovation, and infrastructure				
	Improving public distribution	Sustainable cities and communities				
	Aiming food security	Zero hunger				
	Lead and share knowledge	Quality Education				
	Sharing experience and capabilities with the world	Partnerships for the global				
	Booming economy	Decent work and economic growth				
	Reducing the number of people who are living in poverty	No poverty				
Increasing the production capacity of sustainable energy	Affordable and clean energy	Building up schools				
Empowering women	Gender equality	Providing basic educational infrastructure				
Supporting social security system	Peace, justice, and strong institution	Providing essential educational infrastructure				
Offering job guarantees	Decent work and economic growth					

	Better cleanliness	Clean water and sanitation				
	Construction of toilets	Clean water and sanitation				
	Supporting healthcare	Good health and wellbeing				
	Ensuring food security	Zero hunger				
	Improving food distribution	Zero hunger				
	Saving girl child	Gender equality				
	Self-government for women at village level	Peace, justice, and strong institution				
	Space technology development	Industry, innovation, and infrastructure				
	Improved foreign policy development	Partnerships for the global				
	Developing international alliance	Partnerships for the global				

Focus group Discussions (FGD)

Two FDGs were conducted to understand the perspective of participants who have been exposed to the advertisements. The participants were given four components to place their opinions, ‘their understanding of sustainable development’; ‘the number of SDGs they can recollect from the advertisements’; ‘whether the audio-visual advertisements are an effective way to make people aware of the goals or not’ and ‘their suggestion on the audio-visual ads and towards communicating the SGDs through any other mode’.

‘recycling’				
‘recycling’	Keyword’s frequencies	Students – Group 1	Keyword’s frequencies	Academicians – Group 2
‘recycling’	1	Green energy, sustain life, restricting plastic, carbon emission, safe living, saving earth, grow greenery, sustain forest, waste management, ecological development, preserve nature, save underwater life, SDGs, MDGs.	1	solar energy, natural gas, stop deforestation, stop soil erosion, technological advantages, non-binary, misogyny, air pollution.
	2	Reduce, renewable energy, stop pollution,	2	reduce global warming, improve education,
	3	Reuse, recycling, bio-degradable,	3	Recycling, love your home,
			4	Awareness, gender equality, managing water shortages,
			5	waste management,
6	Natural resources			
‘recycling’	1	renewable energy affordable and clean energy, reproduce industry innovation and infrastructure, natural resources SDG 14, 15, cutting down trees life on land, land erosion climate action, wildlife life on land, education quality education, ecosystem SDG 14, 15, equality gender equality	1	Natural resources SDG 14, 15, water clean water and sanitation, recycle responsible consumption and production, environment SDG 13, 14, 15, poverty No poverty, CSR responsible consumption and production
	2	industrial development industry innovation and infrastructure, environment SDG 13, 14, 15, air pollution responsible consumption and production, climate change climate action,,,,,	2	gender equality gender equality, Goal 17 partnerships for the goals

	3	recycle responsible consumption and production , reuse responsible consumption and production ,,,,,,,	3	education quality education , renewable energy affordable and clean energy
	4	Agricultural development economic growth ,,,,,,,		
	5	clean water clean water and sanitation , poverty No poverty , life underwater life below water , ,,,,,		
‘recycling’	<i>Students (Statements) – Group 1</i>		<i>Academicians (Statements) – Group 1</i>	
‘recycling’	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes • Indirect advertisements are not effective • Not effective 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not for rural audiences • working people will not have time for these ads • indirect ads are very dramatic • few are contradictory • not effective for less educated people • should not become an element of entertainment • not effective • direct ads might be useful 	
‘recycling’	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ads should be informative and entertaining • Celebrity promotion can be helpful • Should focus more on sensitivity towards sustainability • Gender equality be shown more prominently • Awareness programs from the govt. can be beneficial • Hardcore research is to identify their needs and level of perceptions • Banner ads can be helpful, • Common people should promote • Entertaining ads with values can be useful • Individual mindset needs to be changed 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-binaries could be included • Promotion through community radio can be a good way of raising awareness • Audio ads could be a good option • Celebrity endorsement and testimony can work • Poverty should have been displayed more prominently • Goals could be communicated through local ambassadors • Demonstration is important • Inclusion of LGBTQ is important • Could be multilingual, • Poverty, gender equality, hunger, and health could get more focus • Folk media or FDS might transmit these ideas to the rural population, • Poster is a good option • Involving Local Anganwadi, Local doctors, or Asha workers can work better 	

Table 3: Components and responses from controlled group 1 and control group 2

The responses from both the controlled groups were recorded and transcribed for analysis. There are a few keywords which surfaced repeatedly like ‘natural resources’ (six times) ‘waste

management' (five times), 'awareness', 'gender equality', and, 'managing water shortages' (four times) followed by goals with lesser occurrence. While the participants were asked to recall the SDGs, the 'responsible consumption and production' came with the highest number of times, followed by 'clean water and sanitation', 'no poverty', 'life below water', and other goals. A majority of the participants preferred the audio-visual advertisements with a direct approach, a few of them also claimed that the audio-visual ads are not fit to communicate the goals to the mass. The participants were also asked about their suggestions and both groups came up with a handful of them like 'non-binaries should be included', 'ads should be both entertaining as well as informative', 'banner ads might be useful', 'can include celebrity promotion', 'awareness programs from the government should be useful', 'promoting through community radio, local doctors, local ambassadors, Asha or Anganwadi workers could be effective', 'promoting through common people would be more effective' etc.

Discussion and Conclusion

The data derived from the United Nations covering seventeen goals with 169 targets for all of its member nations 'partnership for the global' is clearly in favour with 1690 actions, 123 events, 61 publications followed by 'life below water' (second highest), 'decent work and economic growth' (third highest) and 'no poverty' (fourth highest) and other states. Referring to global performance, the number of nations who have achieved sustainability (across all the goals) is much lesser compared to the nations with significant and major challenges to achieving sustainability. On the other hand, India has improved its score on sustainability over the last seven years, however, the areas like 'industry, innovation and infrastructure' and 'gender equality' still need significant improvement to achieve a decent score.

Advertisements with both direct and indirect approaches were chosen for this study to map the coverage of SDGs from the content and to understand selected individuals' perspectives on their understanding of sustainability through the advertisements. The analysis shows that international ads with a direct approach are covering a large number of SDGs while Indian advertisements with indirect approaches are catering to a minimum number of SDGs. Participants from the FDGs are found to stress on the development of 'recycling' and nurturing 'natural resources' at the bottom level of the SDG wedding cake symbolizing the development of the biosphere. 'Responsible consumption and production' were the 12th goal that came across from the participants the a maximum number of times, which is eventually one of the most developed areas under the SDGs. Advertisements with a direct approach are mostly

preferred by the participants while Indian ads with an indirect approach are referred to as ‘over-dramatic’. Interestingly the suggestions mostly came in favour of involving physical approaches like ‘promotion through local doctors and ambassadors, Anganwadi or Asha workers, community radio’ and also through ‘word of mouth communication’, ‘celebrity endorsement’, and ‘government awareness programs.

Notes

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